

AN EVALUATION OF LINEAR CUMULATIVE DAMAGE (MINER'S LAW) USING KINETIC CRACK GROWTH THEORY

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ABSTRACT: Taking a basis set of creep failure functions as specifying the failure properties for a class of materials, various damage laws can be used to predict failure under any type of stress history. A particularly convenient form is that of Miner's law also known as Linear Cumulative Damage. However, such damage laws are entirely empirical and of uncertain value. A kinetic crack growth theory developed for polymers is used to evaluate Linear Cumulative Damage. LCD is found to be generally unsatisfactory. However, there is an important sub-class of cases where it does perform well, and this can be of importance in an accelerated testing methodology for polymers.

KEY WORDS: kinetic crack growth, linear cumulative damage

INTRODUCTION

Linear Cumulative Damage (LCD), also known as Miner's Law, for application to fatigue failure in materials takes the conventional form

$$\sum_i \frac{\Delta n_i}{n_f(\sigma_i)} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where n_f is the number of cycles to failure at stress level σ_i and Δn_i is the reduced number of cycles applied at each stress level σ_i in a combined program. As given by Miner (1945) relation (1) provides a criterion for fatigue failure under a set of different stress levels. The corresponding form for creep conditions is given by

$$\sum_i \frac{\Delta t_i}{t_c(\sigma_i)} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where t_c is the creep rupture lifetime at stress level σ_i and relation (2) then specifies a criterion for lifetime at multiple stress levels. Relation (2) also is a form of LCD, also known as Miner's Law, and other names as well. Relations (1) and (2) are extremely useful, but entirely empirical. One evidence of their highly idealized and perhaps over simplified nature is that these forms show no sequence dependence. Descriptively, LCD accumulates damage in a linearly additive manner independent of the sequence of the loading applications. The total damage then is used to predict failure. Special interest here is in relation (2) related to creep conditions and its use to represent an arbitrary history leading to failure. Specifically, guidance is here sought on determining the possible conditions of applicability for (2) and conversely the conditions of likely misuse for it.

It is here proposed to use physically based kinetic crack growth theory to evaluate (2). Kinetic crack growth theory in viscoelastic media was developed as a natural generalization of fracture mechanics. Knauss in many references, Knauss (1970, 1974, 1976, 1989), Knauss and Dietmann (1970), Mueller and Knauss (1971) and Schapery in three combined works, Schapery (1975a, b, c), performed the research which completely opened up this field. Many others have added to a discussion of the possibilities and interpretations, from Christensen (1982) through Mulmule and Dempsey (1998) and

Slepyan et al. (1999). The latter two references also give useful bibliographies including summaries. An interesting use of crack growth theory has been in application to life prediction for polymeric materials. See Christensen and Glaser (1994) for an example of this effort. Leon and Weitsman (2001) have given a recent view of this field. The approach taken here builds upon the basic work of Knauss and of Schapery in applying kinetic crack growth theory to problems of practical importance.

The specific crack growth problem of interest here is somewhat more complicated or at least less direct than that usually considered, in the following sense. The entire volume (bulk) of the polymeric material is taken to be at a temperature considerably below the glass transition temperature of the polymer, as often occurs in applications. This is in contrast to materials in the rubbery or transition zone state. Therefore, the bulk material is 'frozen' into the glassy state and to a close approximation behaves in an elastic manner. In this condition, there is no effective source for kinetics in the bulk material and the kinetics may predominately come directly from the crack tip failure process. Behavior of this type can be modeled through the inclusion of rate effects into the cohesive failure zone or process zone model, as has been done by Schapery (1984), Knauss (1993) and Bazant and Li (1997). In this work, this same behavior will be modeled differently through the direct incorporation of rate dependent viscoelastic effects into the surface energy/work term, Γ , in the growing crack formalism. The rationale for this is as follows. With no source for kinetics from the bulk material, a Griffith type energy balance must apply giving a direct relation between the surface energy and the applied stress. It follows that if a change in the stress level causes a change in crack velocity, then the crack surface energy property, Γ , must be crack rate dependent as well. This approach will be developed here.

After obtaining the kinetic crack formalism, it will be used to generate a life prediction methodology based upon how long it takes for a crack of a given initial size to grow to the size causing an instantaneous instability. All this is under a stress state having any prescribed type of history. Finally, after obtaining these forms, LCD will be evaluated by comparison of the LCD predicted lifetimes with kinetic crack growth predicted lifetimes. The methods and assumptions will be explained fully, along with many limitations and restricting conditions.

A KINETIC CRACK GROWTH CRITERION FOR POLYMERS

The problem of interest here is that of a single, isolated crack of length $2a$ in an unbounded isotropic, elastic medium with modulus \hat{E} appropriate to either plane stress or plane strain, and subjected to a transverse, crack opening stress of value(s) $\sigma(t)$ in the far field. The quantity Γ is the surface work content or irrecoverable energy which is expended in advancing the crack by a unit distance. This formulation is not concerned with static crack behavior nor fracture initiation, but rather only applies to the quasi-static crack growth condition in polymeric materials.

For the central crack problem with the bulk material in the glassy, elastic state any time and rate dependent kinetics that are present must come from the crack tip failure region. Thus the controlling and dominant mechanism for crack kinetics for polymers in this state is taken to be the very energetic conditions that exist at the crack tip failure region having large stresses which permit and promote molecular mobility leading to disassociation and failure. In accordance with this condition, assume a controlling viscoelastic equation of the form

$$\Gamma(t) = \int_{t_0}^t \rho_l(t-\tau) \frac{d\sigma_l(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_l(t)$ is some measure of the local failure region stress, $\rho_l(t)$ is a relaxation type (decreasing) function characterizing the failure property and of dimension of length, t_0 is the time of commencement of the failure process and t is the time of completion of the failure process. The means to implement (3) is somewhat involved, and a simpler but related approach will now be taken

by assuming some further conditions. The equivalence of form (3) and the simpler form (4) below will be shown in future work.

In quasi-steady and quasi-static conditions (3) is here replaced by the global form using average stress, σ , which in this case is the far field imposed stress, linearly related to the local stress in (3), as in conventional fracture mechanics. Then

$$I(t) = \rho(t') \sigma(t), \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(t')$ is the relaxation type function governing the failure process, having dimension of length, and where the argument of the relaxation function is weighted at a particular time, t' , to be determined. The use of the relaxation function at the particular time t' in the present quasi-steady state condition is equivalent to using the approximate algebraic relations between relaxation functions and complex moduli with interrelated values of time in the former and steady state frequency in the latter. These algebraic relations, are known to be quite satisfactory for viscoelasticity theory (Christensen, 1982). The particular time t' in (4) must be determined by all the relevant physical quantities, but especially by the crack velocity $\dot{a}(t)$. Thus

$$t' = f(a, \dot{a}, \sigma, \hat{E}). \quad (5)$$

The dependence of t' on \dot{a} is similar to the forms found by Knauss (1974) and Schapery (1975c) for viscoelastic crack growth wherein the creep functions are evaluated at a particular time determined essentially by the crack velocity. The property $\rho(t')$ has the limiting values

$$\rho(t')\big|_{t'=0} = \rho(0) = \rho_0, \quad (6)$$

$$\rho(t')\big|_{t'=\infty} = \rho(\infty) \quad (7)$$

with

$$\rho_0 \ll \rho(\infty). \quad (8)$$

The lower limit $\rho(\infty)$ likely would be very small or perhaps vanish. It will be taken as negligible in the following work.

The Griffith energy balance is taken to apply here because the bulk material is taken to be in the glassy, elastic state. This gives for the central crack problem

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{2\hat{E}\Gamma}{\pi a}, \quad (9)$$

combining (4) and (9) gives

$$\sigma = \frac{2\hat{E}\rho(t')}{\pi a}, \quad (10)$$

where the dependence of σ and a upon t is understood and t' is still given by (5).

From (10) take 'self similar' behavior in σ and a such that they occur in the combination σa . Then (5) becomes

$$t' = f(\sigma a, \dot{a}, \hat{E}). \quad (11)$$

To have the correct dimensions (11) can be written as

$$t' = \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma a}{\hat{E} \dot{a}} \right), \quad (12)$$

where α is a nondimensional parameter that could be found from lifetime data, as will be shown later.

Now combine (10) and (12) to have the formal kinetic crack growth criterion as

$$\sigma = \frac{2\hat{E}}{\pi a} \rho(t) \Big|_{t=\alpha \left(\frac{\sigma a}{\hat{E} \dot{a}} \right)}, \quad (13)$$

where the t' notation has been dropped in favor of the simpler form in (13).

Using (6) and (7), then at the limits of crack velocity, (13) gives

$$\sigma \Big|_{\dot{a} \rightarrow \infty} = \frac{2\hat{E}\rho_0}{\pi a} \quad (14)$$

and

$$\sigma \Big|_{\dot{a} \rightarrow 0} = \frac{2\hat{E}\rho(\infty)}{\pi a}. \quad (15)$$

Using (8) shows that the larger stress drives the crack faster as in (14) and the lower stress drives the crack slower as in (15).

Figure 1. Power law relaxation function, Equation (16).

Power law forms are widely and successfully used as a general representation for viscoelastic properties. Take the power law form for ρ as shown in Figure 1 and given by

$$\rho(t) = \hat{\rho} \cdot \left(\frac{\hat{t}}{t} \right)^n \quad \text{for } \rho(t) < \rho_0, \quad (16)$$

where the exponent n is a positive number, typically considerably less than one. Form (16) then gives

$$\rho(t)_{t=\alpha(\sigma a / \hat{E} \dot{a})} = \rho = \hat{\rho} \left(\frac{\hat{t} \hat{E} \dot{a}}{\alpha \sigma a} \right)^n. \quad (17)$$

With ρ from (17), the complete kinetic crack growth criterion, (13), can be compactly written as

$$\dot{a} = \lambda \cdot (a \sigma)^{\frac{1+n}{n}}, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\hat{t} \hat{E}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\pi}{2 \hat{\rho} \hat{E}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}. \quad (19)$$

For this quasi-steady viscoelastic crack extension of velocity \dot{a} , there is an effective force of magnitude (σa) that drives the growing crack, (18).

LIFE PREDICTION FROM KINETIC CRACK GROWTH

Moving on to life prediction, write the kinetic criterion (18) in the differential form

$$\frac{da}{a^n} = \lambda \cdot \sigma^{\frac{1+n}{n}} dt \quad (20)$$

Integrating (20) gives

$$\frac{1}{(a_0)^{1/n}} - \frac{1}{(a)^{1/n}} = \frac{\lambda}{n} \int_0^t \sigma^{(1+n)/n} d\tau, \quad (21)$$

where a_0 is the initial size of the crack and $a = a(t)$ is the current size of the growing crack. From (14) the growing crack becomes unstable when

$$\sigma(t) = \frac{2 \hat{E} \rho_0}{\pi a(t)} \quad (22)$$

since property ρ_0 controls the instantaneous response. Solving for a from (22) and putting that into (21) gives

$$\frac{1}{(a_0)^{1/n}} - \left(\frac{\pi \sigma}{2 \hat{E} \rho_0} \right)^{1/n} = \frac{\lambda}{n} \int_0^t \sigma^{(1+n)/n} d\tau, \quad (23)$$

where now the upper limit t in the integral has become the lifetime to failure.

The lifetime result (23) is put into nondimensional form by using

$$\tilde{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_s}, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\sigma_s = \frac{2\hat{E}\rho_o}{\pi a_o} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\tilde{t} = \frac{t}{t_1}, \quad (26)$$

where

$$t_1 = \frac{\pi m}{2\alpha} \left(\frac{a_o}{\rho_o} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\hat{\rho}}{\rho_o} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \hat{t}. \quad (27)$$

The stress in (24) is thus nondimensionalized by the instantaneous, static strength σ_s in (25).

Figure 2. Creep rupture lifetime, Equation (29).

With the nondimensional forms in (24-27) and from (19) the lifetime formula (23) becomes

$$1 - \tilde{\sigma}(\tilde{t})^{1/n} = \int_0^{\tilde{t}} \sigma(\tau)^{(1/n)+1} d\tau. \quad (28)$$

Form (28) is the main result of this kinetic crack, lifetime analysis, giving the lifetime \tilde{t} under any prescribed stress history $\tilde{\sigma}(\tau)$. Considering the static strength to be known, there are only two constants or parameters in (28). These are the failure property power law exponent, n , and the time constant t_1 in the nondimensionalized time.

For the case simulating testing to determine the static strength, using $\tilde{\sigma}=1$ in (28) gives $\tilde{t}=0$ meaning instantaneous failure.

For creep condition lifetime, \tilde{t}_c , at constant stress $\tilde{\sigma}$, then (28) gives

$$\tilde{t}_c = \frac{1}{\tilde{\sigma}} \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{\sigma}^n} - 1 \right). \quad (29)$$

The form of (29) is schematically shown in Figure 2. The two constant forms in (28) and thereby in (29) is probably one of the simplest possible creep life-time forms that realistically spreads over many decades of time including both asymptotes. The slope for the power law range asymptote in Figure 2 is given by $-n/(1+n)$ and varying the time constant t_l would cause horizontal shifts on the logarithmic time scale, as in Figure 2.

LINEAR CUMULATIVE DAMAGE

The discrete form of LCD for creep conditions, (2), is written in the more general integral form here as

$$\int_0^t \frac{d\tau}{t_c(\sigma(\tau))} = 1 \quad (30)$$

In order to compare LCD with kinetic crack growth predictions they must have the same basis set of creep lifetime functions. Accordingly, take the set of creep life functions given by (29) in the kinetic crack growth form and insert them into (30) to obtain

$$\int_0^t \frac{d\tau}{\frac{1}{[\tilde{\sigma}(\tau)]^{\frac{1+n}{n}}} - \tilde{\sigma}(\tau)} = 1 \quad (31)$$

It is form (31) that will be used to predict the LCD based failure for a given stress history $\tilde{\sigma}(t)$.

COMPARISON CASES AND EVALUATION

The present kinetic crack theory is given by (28) and the corresponding LCD form by (31). Both are rewritten here in slightly different forms for direct comparison.

The LCD failure criterion (31) is specified by

$$\int_0^{\tilde{t}} \frac{[\tilde{\sigma}(\tau)]^{\frac{1+n}{n}} d\tau}{1 - [\tilde{\sigma}(\tau)]^{\frac{1}{n}}} = 1. \quad (32)$$

The present kinetic crack failure criterion (28) is specified by

$$\frac{1}{1 - [\tilde{\sigma}(\tilde{t})]^{\frac{1}{n}}} \int_0^{\tilde{t}} [\tilde{\sigma}(\tilde{t})]^{\frac{1+n}{n}} d\tau = 1. \quad (33)$$

For a single stress level creep condition, (32) and (33) predict identical creep lifetimes, \tilde{t}_c , as they must for a valid comparison and evaluation.

Relations (32) and (33) appear superficially similar but they actually are fundamentally different. One has a specific sequential history dependence while the other shows no sequence dependence. Although the two forms, (32) and (33), converge for vanishingly small values of the power law exponent, n , specific examples must be probed to be quantitative about the comparison. All numerical results to follow now are found directly from (32) and (33). Comparatively large values of power law index n are taken as providing a rather strenuous test of LCD.

Example 1.

Take $n = 1/4$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 1/4$ up to $\tau = 2.87255$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 3/4$ thereafter
 Then
 $\tilde{t} = 5.745$ LCD
 $\tilde{t} = 5.741$ Kinetic Crack

Example 2.

Take $n = 1/4$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 3/4$ up to $\tau = 2.872554$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 1/4$ thereafter
 Then
 $\tilde{t} = 5.745$ LCD
 $\tilde{t} = 324.8$ Kinetic Crack

Example 3.

Take $n = 1/4$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 0.95$ up to $\tau = 0.23$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 1/2$ thereafter
 Then
 $\tilde{t} = 1.447$ LCD
 $\tilde{t} = 24.54$ Kinetic Crack

Example 4.

Take $n = 1/10$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 0.95$ up to $\tau = 0.68$
 $\tilde{\sigma} = 1/2$ thereafter
 Then
 $\tilde{t} = 74.51$ LCD
 $\tilde{t} = 1255$ Kinetic Crack

In Example 1 the two load levels are taken with equal durations according to the LCD predicted lifetime. The lower load level comes first, and the higher load level follows. LCD and Kinetic crack give nearly identical predictions for lifetimes. The reason for this is quite apparent, the first load level in each case has an insignificant effect upon the damage state as compared with the second larger level.

In Example 2 the sequence of the two load levels in Example 1 is reversed. The LCD lifetime prediction is unchanged due to its sequence independence. However, the kinetic crack prediction is very strongly effected and the comparison is poor.

The last two examples at $n = 1/4$ and $n = 1/10$ examine cases where a strongly damaging load level is applied followed by the determination of the remaining lifetime at a much lower load level simulating a service condition. In both examples the initial loads are at 95% of the static strength and held for about 96% of what would be the lifetimes at that level. The LCD and kinetic crack lifetimes are over an order of magnitude different.

The general conclusion within the present evaluation methodology is that Linear Cumulative Damage produces misleading results. It can be in error by orders of magnitude. There is however an important exception to this generally unsatisfactory behavior of LCD. Example 1 suggests that for stress levels that are always increasing and reasonably regular LCD is surprisingly good. This behavior can also be rationalized directly from the general forms of (32) and (33). A particular case for this benign class of loading types is given by constant strain rate conditions, possibly extending into long times. This condition is employed by Miyano et al. (1997, 1999) in an accelerated testing methodology.

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